

WORKSHOP
ENDURE

Inequalities, Community Resilience and New
Governance Modalities in a Post-Pandemic World

**The Utility of Resilience
Frameworks for Examining
COVID-19 Outcomes and Societal
Transformations in the COVID-19
Period**

13-14 March 2025

University of Campinas, Brazil

ABSTRACTS

ENDURE PROJECT'S INSTITUTIONS

State University of Campinas — Unicamp

University of São Paulo — USP

Federal University of Amazonas — UFAM

State University of Rio de Janeiro — UERJ

Federal University of Rio de Janeiro — UFRJ

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Finland: University of Helsinki, PI Emilia Palonen

Poland: University of Wrocław, PI Mateusz Karolak

United Kingdom: Glasgow Caledonian University, PI James Foley

Croatia: Institute for Development and International Relations (IRMO), PI Senada Selo Šabić

Colombia: National University of Colombia, PI Tania Pérez-Bustos

United States: University of Texas Health Science Center at Houston, PI Eric C. Jones

Canada: Université Laval, PI Philippe Bourbeau

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INSTITUTIONAL SUPPORT

Instituto de Geociências da UNICAMP

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THE PROJECT

The deepening of inequalities, the challenges of governance, and the intensification of dis/misinformation in the post-Covid-19 world are some of the themes addressed by the project “ENDURE: Inequalities, Community Resilience and New Governance Modalities in a Post-Pandemic World,” which brought together researchers from 11 countries (Brazil, Germany, Colombia, the United Kingdom, Canada, Finland, the United States, Croatia, Poland, Romania, and Turkey) to analyze the short- and long-term consequences of the pandemic.

Funded by the “Trans-Atlantic Platform for Social Sciences and Humanities (T-AP)” through the São Paulo Research Foundation (FAPESP) since 2022, the project has generated innovative and critical reflections on emerging issues. Analyzing the consequences of the pandemic on formal and informal employment dynamics, the project provides insights for policy formulation aiming economic sustainability and improving working conditions in a scenario of rapid social transformations. The project works with traditional communities and local governments, in turn, fostered closer ties between universities and society. These interactions contributed to a more plural and critical view of contemporary challenges. The analysis shows how local solidarity networks promoted governance and resilience practices which can contribute to the protection of ecosystems and the promotion of sustainability policies.

Workshop, 12th to 14th of March of 2025

Following an open call that attracted researchers beyond the project's existing network of collaborators, the team held discussions at the Institute of Geosciences (IG) at Unicamp between March 12 and 14 during the international workshop. The hybrid event featured the presentation of 25 research papers and brought together experts from 11 countries: Brazil, Germany, Colombia, the United Kingdom, Canada, Finland, the United States, Croatia, Poland, Romania, and Turkey.

Among the universities represented, in addition to Unicamp, were: the Federal University of Amazonas (UFAM), the State University of Rio de Janeiro (UERJ), the Federal University of São Paulo (Unifesp), and São Paulo State University (UNESP), as well as Freie Universität Berlin (FU Berlin), the University of Helsinki, the University of Wrocław, Glasgow Caledonian University, the Institute for Development and International Relations (IRMO), the National University of Colombia, the University of Texas at Houston, Université Laval, and Özyeğin University.

The event marked the beginning of the final phase of the ENDURE project, funded since 2022 by the Trans-Atlantic Platform for Social Sciences and Humanities (T-AP), which includes agencies such as FAPESP (Brazil), DFG (Germany), AKA (Finland), HRZZ (Croatia), MINCIENCIAS (Colombia), NCN (Poland), NSF (USA), SSHRC (Canada), and UKRI-ESRC (United Kingdom). This notebook compiles the abstracts of the presented papers, the authors' contact information and biographies.

PROGRAM

12 March (wednesday)

9:00 - Project hybrid meeting

14:30 (departure from IG) - Tour to Sirius – Brazilian Synchrotron Light Laboratory

17:30 - Dinner

13 March (Tuesday)

Institute of Geosciences / UNICAMP

9:45 - Welcome Ceremony

10:00 - Opening Conference

12:00 - Lunch

13:00 - Panel 1: Governance and Policy Responses to Covid-19

14:30 - Break

14:45 - Panel 2: Education and Resilience During the Pandemic

17:30 - Happy Hour - CPV / UNICAMP

14 March (Friday)

Institute of Geosciences / UNICAMP

9:00 - Panel 3: Social Mobilization and Activism

10:45 - Panel 4: Community Resilience and Local Response

13:00 - Panel 5: Health, Misinformation, and Public Perception

14:45 - Panel 6: Global and Cross-National Perspectives on Resilience

16:30 - Closure

PANELS

Panel 1: Governance and Policy Responses to Covid-19

Moderator: **Kleber Carrilho (University of Helsinki)**

Discussant: **Mihai Varga (FU Berlin)**

Time slot – **13:00-14:30** (horário local), **17:00-18:30** (CET)

On-site: sala IG218

<https://uu-se.zoom.us/j/69727558145?from=addon>

1. Effectiveness of Social Isolation Measures in Amazonas: The Critical Role of Timeliness During the Covid-19 Pandemic (Henrique Pereira - UFAM)
2. Navigating Sanitation Challenges in Brazil: Political Discourses and Actions During Covid-19 (Lara Ramos - UNICAMP)
3. Building Lasting Trust: Analyzing the Resilience of Science-to-Policy Institutions in Quebec and Sweden During the Covid-19 Pandemic (Antoine Lemor - Université de Montréal)
4. Crisis Communication During Covid-19: Comparative Analysis of Finland and Brazil (Kleber Carrilho, Emilia Palonen, Juha Koljonen - University of Helsinki) online

Panel 2: Education and Resilience During the Pandemic

Moderator: **Gabriela Villen (UNICAMP)**

Discussant: **Eric Jones (University of Texas)**

Time slot: **14:45-16:15** (horário local), **18:45-20:15** (CET)

On-site: sala IG218

<https://uu-se.zoom.us/j/69727558145?from=addon>

1. Resilience and Adaptation: Analyzing the Impact of Covid-19 on Elementary Education in Limeira, São Paulo (Ingrid Barbosa Betty, Sandra Gemma, Sandra Beltran - UNICAMP)
2. The Impact of Covid-19 on Study Practices: Insights from Higher Education Aspirants Enskillment in Brazil and the U.S. (Leonardo Henrique Brandão Monteiro - UNESP)
3. Analysis of the Capacity for Resilience and Innovation in the Return to In-Person Classes in a Municipal Public Education System in São Paulo (Cristiane Tavares, Eduardo Marandola Jr, Elke Stedefeldt - UNICAMP) online
4. Resilience and Resistance: The GECA Women's Initiative in Nhunguara During the Covid-19 Pandemic (Maíra Rodrigues da Silva et al. - UNICAMP)

Panel 3: Social Mobilization and Activism

Moderators: **Aline Yuri Hasegawa e Marina Martinelli (UNICAMP)**

Discussant: **Soner Barthoma (FU Berlin)**

Time-slot: **09:00-10:30** (horário local), **13:00-14:30** (CET)

On-site: sala IG211

<https://uu-se.zoom.us/j/68649274480?from=addon>

1. Textile Activism in Colombia: Social Mobilization Through Fabric During the Pandemic
2. (Isabel González Arango, Sylvia Gómez Gómez, Tania Pérez Bustos - Universidad Nacional de Colômbia) online
3. Evolution of social responses to Covid-19 governance in Poland - between compliance and contestation, between complimenting and correcting (Wojciech Ufel, Anna Cichecka, Mateusz Karolak - University of Wrocław) online
4. Civic mobilization and limits of governance: Social responses to Covid-19 in Croatia (Senada S. Sabic & Emina Buzinkic - IRMO) online
5. Photographic Performances in Crisis: Small Enterprises and Crowdfunding During Covid-19 and the Russia-Ukraine War (Virpi Salojärvi and Maria Eronen-Valli - University of Helsinki) online

Panel 4: Community Resilience and Local Response

Moderator: **Ann Nguyen (University of Texas)**

Discussants: **Henrique Pereira (INPA/UFAM)**

Time slot: **10:45-12:30** (local time), **14:45-16:15** (CET)

On-site: sala IG211

<https://uu-se.zoom.us/j/68649274480?from=addon>

1. Resilience strategies during Covid-19: the context and examples at the favela complex of La Maré in Rio de Janeiro, Brazil (Liliana Acero - UFRJ) online
2. Community experiences, individual and collective actions in the context of the Covid-19 pandemic: the interrelationships between nature/culture and society in the sustainability of good living (José Maria Trajano Vieira et al. - UFAM) online
3. Early Results from a Survey Study on Community Resilience among Assyrians in Turkey (Soner Barthoma - FU Berlin)
4. A Crisis Within Crises: Narratives of Food Insecurity and Coping for Syrian Refugees in Turkey. (Inci Aksu Kargin & Susan Rottmann - University of Özyegin)
5. Demography, social inscription and ideology: determinants of the relation of Brazilians with the Covid-19 pandemic (Adalberto Cardoso - IESP-UERJ and Leda Gitahy - UNICAMP)

Panel 5: Health, Misinformation, and Public Perception

Moderator: **Eric Jones** (University of Texas) | Discussant: **Susan Rottmann** (University of Özyegin)

Time slot – **13:15-14:45** (local time), **17:15-18:45** (CET)

Zoom link: <https://uu-se.zoom.us/j/68649274480?from=addon>

On-site: Room IG218

1. Ivermectin in pandemic Brazil: a cross-sectional analysis between Twitter/X and other sources of mis/dis/information (Jean Medeiros, Fabio Malini, Leda Gitahy - UNICAMP) online
2. The struggle about masks and mask recommendation – Contestation of Finnish mask discussion on Twitter during

the Covid-19 pandemic in 2020 and 2021(Kleber Carrilho, Emilia Palonen, Juha Koljonen - University of Helsinki) online

3. Unequal Burdens: The Impact of Covid-19 on Brazil's Diverse Populations and Community Resilience (Aline Hasegawa et al. - UNICAMP)
4. Inter-scientificity, religiosity and traditional knowledge in the fight against Covid-19 among indigenous peoples on the Amazonian borders (José Maria Trajano Vieira - UFAM) online

Panel 6: Global and Cross-National Perspectives on Resilience

Moderator: **Aline Hasegawa** (UNICAMP) | Discussant: **Antoine Lemor** (Université de Montréal)

Time slot – **15:00-16:45** (local time), **19:00-20:30** (CET)

Zoom link: <https://uu-se.zoom.us/j/68649274480?from=addon>

On-site: Room IG218

1. Post-COVID Transformations in Culture, Social Structure and Policy in Relation to Mass Emergencies in Several American and European Countries (Ann Nguyen, Eric Jones - University of Texas)
2. Preliminary Findings from Cross-National Surveys on Experiences of the Covid-19 Pandemic, Political Attitudes, and Resilience (Kristinn Arsaelsson & Peter Ramand - University of Wisconsin) online
3. Global Crisis and Local Livelihoods: Understanding Biographical Adjustments (Mihai Varga - FU Berlin)

4. Spatial-Temporal Analysis of Resilience to COVID in Europe and the Americas (Jingjing Gao, Eric Jones - University of Texas)

ABSTRACTS

Effectiveness of Social Isolation Measures in Amazonas: The Critical Role of Timeliness During the Covid-19 Pandemic

Henrique Pereira, Universidade Federal do Amazonas (UFAM)

This study analyses the effectiveness of the social isolation measures adopted by 57 municipalities in Amazonas to combat the Covid-19 pandemic, based on data monitored by the Atlas ODS Amazonas project. The focus is on the relationship between the timeliness of government actions and the type of measures implemented with the number of cases registered by 21 May 2020. The results indicate that the speed with which the measures were implemented was the determining factor for their effectiveness, regardless of the nature of these actions. Municipalities that adopted stricter measures, such as territorial blockades, showed a reduced number of cases, especially when these measures were introduced soon after the first case was registered. For example, Novo Airão managed to 'flatten the curve' of contagion due to the early adoption of rigorous actions, while Tefé, despite implementing similar measures, did so late, resulting in less effectiveness. Additionally, the study highlights that even less stringent measures can be effective if implemented early, as observed in Careiro da Várzea. Another relevant point is that actions introduced late require greater rigour to be effective, although this approach entails high social and economic costs. In addition, monitoring and enforcement are considered fundamental to guaranteeing the effectiveness of social isolation measures. The study concludes that swift and decisive government action is essential to contain epidemic outbreaks. Effective communication strategies and the constant adaptation of measures to the epidemiological situation are also recommended. However, it should be noted that the data analysed is limited to the period up to May 2020, and the results may not be generalisable to other regions or times of the pandemic.

Navigating Sanitation Challenges in Brazil: Political Discourses and Actions During Covid-19

Lara Ramos, University of Campinas (UNICAMP)

As the Covid-19 pandemic sprawled across every continent, 'hand-washing' became the official guideline to prevent contagion. In this scenario, governmental and non-governmental actors mobilised to promote the provision of water supply and customer services to the largest number of people. With the imposed isolation, virtual events became the centre of the political debate, bringing to light strategies and challenges to guarantee basic needs, debated within the scope of the federal legislative and executive branches and civil society. The purpose of this article is to explore the discourses produced and the interventions proposed between April and May 2020. In the light of social studies of science and technology and discussions regarding the enactment and production of the state, mapped through the actions of key actors, this ethnography enables us to outline the conflicts of sanitation governance in Brazil.

Building Lasting Trust: Analyzing the Resilience of Science-to-Policy Institutions in Quebec and Sweden During the Covid-19 Pandemic

Antoine Lemor, Université de Montréal

This article examines institutional resilience—commonly defined as the ability of institutions to absorb, adapt, and respond effectively to external shocks while maintaining their core functions, but here specifically focusing on the capacity to sustain a long-term, trust-based relationship with the population in pursuit of shared policy objectives (such as combating a pandemic)—by comparing the public health responses of Quebec and Sweden during the Covid-19 pandemic. In Sweden, the Public Health Agency operated with substantial autonomy in relation to the government, whereas Quebec’s National Institute of Public Health (INSPQ) was more closely integrated into a politically centralized approach. Drawing on comparable yet previously uncombined public opinion data from both countries—covering adherence to public health measures, trust in government, population anxiety, vaccination, and risk perception—this study investigates how different institutional arrangements shape the public’s ability to cope with the crisis and maintain confidence in health agencies and institutions. Supplemented by a review of official pandemic evaluation reports from both jurisdictions, the analysis underscores key organizational factors that contribute to this form of institutional resilience. Ultimately, this comparative inquiry underlines which institutional configurations are more likely to uphold public trust, support individuals’ capacity to withstand the crisis, and effectively manage health emergencies, thereby guiding the development of robust and adaptive public health governance structures.

Covid-19, government communication and social media: the experiences of Finland and Brazil

Kleber Carrilho, Emilia Palonen, Juha Koljonen - University of Helsinki (online)

This work examines the divergent approaches to public communication during the Covid-19 pandemic in Finland and Brazil, highlighting the role of governance structures, political leadership, and social media dynamics. As part of the ENDURE project, which investigates post-pandemic governance and community resilience, this comparative study analyzes how official communication strategies and social media discourse influenced public perception and adherence to containment measures. Using a mixed-methods approach, including interpretative topic modeling and hashtag landscape analysis of over six million tweets, the research explores the interplay between scientific communication, political rhetoric, and misinformation.

Finland's centralized, science-driven response, led by Prime Minister Sanna Marin and health authorities, prioritized transparency and consensus. Despite early criticisms on social media for perceived insufficient measures, the government maintained public trust through coordinated press briefings and deference to experts. The Finnish strategy emphasized hierarchical yet collaborative decision-making, balancing scientific advice with political accountability. However, regional administrative conflicts and evolving public debates revealed challenges in sustaining consensus as the pandemic progressed.

In contrast, Brazil's fragmented federal structure and polarized leadership under President Jair Bolsonaro led to a disjointed response. The federal government's dismissal of scientific recommendations, promotion of unproven treatments, and clashes with state-level policies fueled misinformation and social division. Twitter emerged as a battleground for ideological disputes, amplifying anti-vaccine rhetoric and undermining public health efforts. The lack of cohesive communication exacerbated distrust, with Bolsonaro's denialist stance contradicting technical authorities and deepening societal polarization.

Key differences lie in governance coherence, trust in science, and social media's role. Finland's centralized, evidence-based approach fostered resilience and adherence, while Brazil's politicized discourse hindered effective crisis management. The study underscores the importance of unified leadership, science-aligned communication, and adaptive governance in mitigating public health crises. These findings contribute to understanding how institutional frameworks and digital platforms shape crisis responses, offering lessons for enhancing resilience in future global emergencies.

Resilience and Adaptation: Analyzing the Impact of Covid-19 on Elementary Education in Limeira, São Paulo

Ingrid Barbosa Betty, Sandra Gemma, Sandra Beltran , UNICAMP

The Covid-19 syndemic transformed the way human vital activity—work—was practiced. This study aimed to understand the transformations in the teaching activity system at a public elementary school in Limeira, São Paulo, from 2020 to 2023. The theoretical framework included Cultural-Historical Activity Theory, Activity Ergonomics, Socio-Historical Psychology, Psychology in the Integral Management of Risks, Emergencies, and Disasters, as well as the Sociology of Work and Disasters. Data collection was conducted at three levels: micro (teachers), meso (school management), and macro (Department of Education).

Additionally, formative intervention techniques from the Change Laboratory were applied to promote expansive learning regarding the teaching activity system. The results enabled the construction of change matrices that related disaster phases (prevention, mitigation, preparedness, response, and recovery) to different modes of teaching (in-person, emergency remote, hybrid, and return to in-person) and the work-related transformations identified by the teachers.

The study revealed a strengthening of collective networks within the school context, as well as challenges related to work overload, self-imposed demands, and the limitations of emergency remote teaching. The difficulties faced by teachers were acknowledged by the school management team and members of the municipal Department of Education. During the application of the Change Laboratory method, participants demonstrated an increased awareness of their role in ensuring the teaching-learning process.

Finally, all collected data were organized into five categories of analysis: losses, deaths, and grief in teaching work; working or merely following rules?; three years in one; public insecurity and education; educating and surviving the Covid-19 disaster.

The Impact of Covid-19 on Study Practices: Insights from Higher Education Aspirants Enskillment in Brazil and the U.S.

Leonardo Henrique Brandão Monteiro, UNESP

Our investigation into how higher education aspirants studied outside the school environment began in 2019. This research aimed to understand these study dynamics by focusing on how students embodied some skills, such as concentration, memory, and body discipline, during this process. Ingold's (2011) concept of enskillment, which focuses on developing skills through practice, was pivotal then. In 2020, Covid-19 spread globally. Adaptations and new protocols were needed since the research covered universities of São Paulo State, Brasil, and from the Bay Area, California, U.S. The investigation explored the higher education students' preparation for university selections through questionnaires with open and Likert-scale questions and one-on-one interviews—based on Vermersch's (2018) explicitation interview. In the questionnaire, 83% of the students selected 'totally agree' to the statement: "The Covid-19 pandemic radically changed how people study at home."

The main findings suggest that students admitted to Brazilian universities had some resources—such as Internet access, a desk and/or dedicated study space, books, and textbooks—in their homes, allowing them to study for entrance exams (vestibulares). The U.S. interlocutors, who had similar environments, described adaptations to the pandemic context and a de-enskillment of their studies abilities due to the change of expectations, particularly among students from public schools. Also, it found a difference between public school and private school attendees in Brasil. The first group significantly reported difficulties in surpassing learning gaps, while private school attendees highlighted struggles and worries caused by the pandemic, poor time management, and/or family pressure to get into university. Both scenarios, with their particularities, showed the necessity of some structure for developing the abilities cited before and highlighted inequalities in higher education access during the pandemic.

Analysis of the Capacity for Resilience and Innovation in the Return to In-Person Classes in a Municipal Public Education System in São Paulo (online)

Cristiane Tavares, UNIFESP; **Eduardo Marandola Jr**, UNICAMP; **Elke Stedefeldt**, UNIFESP

Covid-19 has had a significant impact on education, requiring the education system to demonstrate resilience in facing health risks and enabling the reopening of schools. This study aimed to analyze the resilience and innovation capacity of the educational structure in response to the return and continuity of in-person classes within a municipal public school system in São Paulo. It is an excerpt from a broader study on vulnerability, the risk of Covid-19, and resilience. Based on interviews with education system professionals, documents, and analysis of vulnerability and risk, the data were categorized using a traffic light system and incorporated into Resilience Matrices (primary domains x stages of disaster management).

The results indicated a lack of actions in the preparation phase. In the assimilation phase, efforts were made to adapt facilities, equipment, and structures despite the challenges; however, information was delivered in a fragmented manner and was not always accessible to all stakeholders, with unclear and vague language. During the recovery phase, difficulties were observed in maintaining essential items, such as hygiene supplies, a problem that worsened over time. In the adaptation phase, institutions were less prepared than before the pandemic, with no significant structural changes.

The perception of risk decreased after schools reopened, and although there was an understanding of the pandemic and the importance of protective measures, this awareness was limited to that specific period. Measures implemented to protect against more than just SARS-CoV-2 were not sustained, leading to the abandonment of hygiene practices.

It is concluded that the education system demonstrated a high capacity for recovery but a low capacity for adaptation. Although it overcame the initial challenges of returning to in-person classes, the structure remains unprepared for a similar event, highlighting a tension between the capacity for adaptation and unresolved structural limitations.

Resilience and Resistance: The GECA Women's Initiative in Nhunguara During the Covid-19 Pandemic

Máira Rodrigues da Silva; Carla Ladeira Pimentel Águas; Ana Carolina Marcucci Oliveira; Ana Carolina Dias Silva; Cíntia de Paula Nascimento; Erica Gonçalves Dias; Joabi da Silva Santos; Lucas Silva Rodrigues; Manuela de Carvalho Rodrigues; Manuela Gomes Rocha; Marina Fontolan; Matheus Barros, UNICAMP

This paper explores the connections between resilience, resistance and adaptability from the concrete experience of the women's group Guerreiras Empoderadas Cultivando e Aprendendo – GECA (Empowered Warriors Cultivating and Learning), located in the black rural community (quilombo) of Nhunguara, in the Vale do Ribeira region, São Paulo, Brazil. The strong presence of Afro-descendant communities in the region is linked to the use of enslaved labour for gold mining, especially from the 17th century onwards.

In order to guarantee food security and make an income during the Covid-19 pandemic, the women mobilised to plant manioc plots using the Traditional Agricultural System and started producing flour.

The concept of resilience refers to the capacity of a system to absorb a disturbance and reorganise itself while going through a process of change, and is central to the discussion on community agency and involvement (Hall and Lamont, 2013). The GECA group's initiative allows us to reflect upon aspects such as female protagonism in contexts of vulnerability and the ability to cope with a threat based on the alliance between local knowledge and new technologies.

This work is the result of participatory strategies, based on an interdisciplinary and multi-epistemic vision. Together with the GECA group, we organized a Community Resilience Laboratory (ComRes Lab) resulting, among other developments, in a collective planting of a manioc field and the production of a book with colloquial language and a paradidactic vocation, signed by both members of the Unicamp team and the community. Emphasizing the relevance of local knowledge and dialogue between different sources of knowledge for community resilience, the publication aims to extend this discussion and related themes to wider audiences.

Textile Activism in Colombia: Social Mobilization Through Fabric During the Pandemic

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During 2020 and 2022, in the midst of the pandemic and the social outburst in Colombia, textile language became a technology of denunciation and a space for collective and pacific encounter. These material ways of social mobilization resignified genealogies of textile activism that, since the end of the 90s, emerged in Colombia in the context of the armed conflict and the defense of human rights.

In order to understand these material technologies of social protest and the repertoires that configure them, we analyze 26 textile activism initiatives, in 7 departments and 13 cities in the country that emerged during this period. We identify new forms of mobilization that weave together indignation and collective hope, creating genuine and autonomous forms of non-violent citizen participation that resonate with an understanding of politics, not only as a struggle for power, but also as conflict management based on networks of knowledge and solidarity.

Civic mobilization and limits of governance: Social responses to Covid-19 in Croatia (online)

Senada S. Sabic & Emina Buzinkic, IRMO

This article examines the complex interplay of social and political dynamics during the Covid-19 pandemic in Croatia, focusing on emergent organizing and the long-term societal transformations triggered or channeled by the Covid-19 crisis governance. This paper explores how disruption of everyday politics and economy expose underlying tensions between state authority, civic resistance, and forms of social organizing.

Motivated by the broader question of how societies react to upheaval, we analyze anti-vaccination protests as a form of opposition to state-imposed public health measures. This case highlights the fragility of regulatory power when confronted with organized dissent and the difficulties of state enforcement in the face of the protest. At the same time, the pandemic revealed instances of grassroots mobilization in contexts where state intervention was absent—whether due to a lack of political will, institutional capacity, or strategic engagement. Beyond institutional responses, community-driven solidarity initiatives emerged, often in defiance of official mandates such as lockdowns and movement restrictions.

Through small-scale acts of support and larger mutual aid efforts, people supported one another, forming networks of trust and care that operated outside traditional state structures and civil society. These examples illustrate how civic resistance is not limited to protest but can also take the form of decentralized, collective action that reconnects communities and reconfigures social dynamics.

Photographic Performances in Crisis: Small Enterprises and Crowdfunding During Covid-19 and the Russia-Ukraine War (online)

Virpi Salojärvi and Maria Eronen-Valli, University of Helsinki

This study explores how two mega-crises—the Covid-19 pandemic and the Russia–Ukraine war—are portrayed in photographic performances of crowdfunding campaign calls by small- and medium-sized enterprises. These companies, aside from being commercial actors, are crisis experiencers and eyewitnesses making visual meanings of crises across media platforms. This study examines visuals (166 photographs, 43 photo collages, 25 GIFs, and 23 videos) in 54 crisis-related crowdfunding campaign calls (19 Finnish, 18 North American, and 17 Ukrainian) on three different platforms. The data are analyzed with a focus on visual rhetoric. The study contributes to previous visual analyses by finding five connotations: suffering, endurance, resistance, peer support, and hope. In this era of mega-crises, crowdfunding has become a discursive site for both promotional and testimonial performances, varying from a private to communal focus. Considering future visual analyses of crises, this study suggests enthymematic and metonymic representations as tools to explore visuals with merged aims.

Demography, social inscription and ideology: determinants of the relation of Brazilians with the Covid-19 pandemic

Adalberto Cardoso, IESP-UERJ and **Leda Gitahy**, UNICAMP

The article will analyse the results of the Endure survey (Cluster 3), and will explore three dimensions of the possible explanation of the Brazilians' attitudes towards the public policies to combat the sanitary crisis of the Covid-19 pandemic: demography, meaning the intersectionality of gender, race, generation, education and geographical region; social inscription, meaning labour market participation and occupational position (formal/informal); and ideology, meaning attitudes towards democracy, political participation and political institutions. We intend to show that people's social and economic inscription have little to say about their attitudes about Covid-19 and how they acted to protect themselves. Much of these are explained by how and where they position themselves in the political spectrum, in a very polarized society.

Resilience strategies during Covid-19: the context and examples at the favela complex of Maré in Rio de Janeiro, Brazil (online)

Liliana Acero, UFRJ

Resilience refers to the ability of a population, community, or an individual to respond to different forms of shock, risk, adversity, and disturbances in ways that enable adaptation to these stressors, and the renewal or transformation of a previous state. The concept, widely applied in social science research, can be understood in diverse ways, with ambiguities about adversity and positive adaptation. Resilience strategies have also different political implications for specific social subjects and agencies. The aim of this study is to describe the context and the ways in which resilient strategies were applied in a peripheral community of Rio de Janeiro Brazil: the favela complex La Maré. The conceptual perspective followed is culturally and gender oriented and critical of neoliberal approaches to resilience. Methodologically, the study involves a selective appraisal of theoretical frameworks and secondary information that can be articulated to address the strategies local NGOs, other civic organizations and individuals followed to confront and protect themselves during the COVID 9 pandemic, given the absence of any clear and adequate public policy. Among local NGOs working in the field, Redes da Maré was a key leader in the organization of protective strategies and worked closely with a vaccination programme designed by a prominent scientific organization, the Foundation Oswaldo Cruz (FIOCRUZ). The paper explores mainly the context of La Maré, the way resources were distributed, health care was developed, publications were distributed and information accessed by its inhabitants. Findings show a relative reduction of infections and deaths within the complex, as well as a high level of engagement among residents in the short and long term: from adaptability to resilience. Moreover, findings also show the forms of democratic resistance established within and between local NGOs, academic and municipal organizations, as well as the cooperation with other peripheral communities.

Community experiences, individual and collective actions in the context of the Covid-19 pandemic: the interrelationships between nature/culture and society in the sustainability of good living (online)

José Maria Trajano Vieira; Luciane Samias Forte; Tatiana Samias Mapiama; Bete da Costa Falcon; Sabrina Ataíde Vargas; Raiciane Venâncio Alves; Elizângela Lopes, UFAM

Produced by many hands and minds, the text of this communication is the result of individual and collective reflections based on field experiences of an anthropologist and professor/supervisor of Kokama researchers residing in riverside, indigenous, and urban communities. These communities directly faced the specter of the Covid-19 pandemic, which haunted them with anguish, insecurity, and uncertainty but also brought hope, empowerment, and revitalization of traditional native knowledge in the face of an invisible enemy—the coronavirus.

For centuries, the Kokama people have resisted the political and social adversities that afflict them. These young Kokama women, most of them mothers, engaged in various ways and created or strengthened associations to claim collective rights—territorial rights, education, healthcare, and linguistic and cultural appreciation. Despite external pressures to deny their identities and ancestral knowledge, the Kokama people, following their traditions, employed numerous strategies to prevent and mitigate coronavirus infection.

Methodology

As social distancing recommendations and restrictions allowed, assemblies, meetings, events, field practices, and extension projects were organized both at the university and in the communities of Alto Solimões, such as Bom Jardim, Nova Aliança, Santo Antônio, Santa Luzia, Guanabara 2, São Gabriel, and Igarapé do Manacá, as well as in the Javari River region, including São Pedro do Norte, Palmarí, and Nova Aldeia. These activities, along with personal observations, interviews, audio and video recordings, and field notebook annotations, formed the foundation of the descriptions and analyses presented here.

We hope that sharing these diverse experiences contributes to the state of the art in research on the multiple consequences of the pandemic for humanity—not only as chaos and trauma but also in terms of the resilience and resistance that emerged in this context of local, ethnic, and border-specific challenges. Furthermore, this work aims to explore how to ensure the sustainability of indigenous well-being practices.

Evolution of social responses to Covid-19 governance in Poland - between compliance and contestation, between complementing and correcting (online)

Wojciech Ufel, Anna Cichecka, Mateusz Karolak, University of Wrocław

This paper examines the evolution of societal responses to Covid-19 governance in Poland using the 4C framework, which categorizes reactions along the axes of acknowledgment of state effectiveness and degree of support or opposition. Drawing

on 11 interviews with leaders of social protests, desk research, and a literature review, the study juxtaposes governmental perspectives with grassroots mobilization. Two key protest movements—the Women’s Strike and the Entrepreneur’s Strike—serve as case studies to illustrate how compliance, complementing, contestation, and correction strategies have been employed. Findings reveal that while contestation remained a dominant response, hybrid strategies emerged, with activists selectively complying with regulations, engaging in local-level cooperation, and correcting state failures through grassroots initiatives. The results highlight the adaptability of civil society in crisis governance, the dynamics of power between social movements and political structures, and the ambiguous role of class-based mobilization in Poland’s protest landscape.

Early Results from a Survey Study on Community Resilience among Assyrians in Turkey

Soner Barthoma, FU Berlin & Uppsala University

This paper shares preliminary findings from a survey study examining community resilience among Assyrian communities in Southeast Turkey and Istanbul. Focusing on historical and contemporary adversities—including forced displacement, land dispossession, and persistent marginalization—the study investigates how Assyrians navigate threats to cultural survival and community cohesion. Special attention is given to coping strategies amid large-scale emigration to Western countries and its implications for collective identity. By highlighting these dynamics, the research sheds light on the interplay between resilience, displacement, and cultural preservation in a marginalized indigenous group.

A Crisis Within Crises: Narratives of Food Insecurity and Coping for Syrian Refugees in Turkey.

Inci Aksu Kargin & Susan Rottmann, University of Özyegin

Syrian refugees in Turkey face significant challenges in accessing adequate and nutritious food, a situation exacerbated by their precarious living conditions and several external shocks like the Covid-19 pandemic, economic crisis, and the 2023 earthquake. Yet, little research has examined how these refugees perceive their food needs and cope with food insecurity. This article fills this gap by utilizing the Food and Agriculture Organization's framework for studying food security, which encompasses availability, access, utilization, and stability. Through 27 semi-structured interviews, the study explores how refugees handle food insecurity, including by limiting food quantity and diversity, borrowing money and food, and prioritizing children's nutrition. Furthermore, the study highlights the governance dimension of food security, demonstrating how policies and market forces affect refugees' vulnerability to hunger. By adopting a qualitative approach focused on migrants' narratives and experiences, this article provides a nuanced, micro-level understanding of food insecurity. It examines the cultural and social aspects of this issue for refugees, while also offering recommendations for policymakers and humanitarian organizations who aim to mitigate this crisis within a crisis.

Ivermectin in pandemic Brazil: a cross-sectional analysis between Twitter/X and other sources of mis/dis/information

Jean Medeiros, Fabio Malini, Leda Gitahy, UNICAMP

During the Covid-19 pandemic, Ivermectin became a polarizing and multifaceted issue, igniting debates across societal, scientific, and political spheres. This paper examines the dissemination, use, and study of Ivermectin in Brazil during two distinct periods: June 8–16, 2020, and January 4–11, 2021. Using varied visualizations, we analyze narratives on Twitter/X, focusing on the evolution of public perceptions, political influences, and scientific insights of the drug. The study highlights complex interactions among social actors—politicians, medical professionals, scientists, laypeople, and institutions—offering diverse perspectives on the topic.

To construct the analysis, datasets of posts mentioning “Ivermectin” were collected from Twitter/X, a platform pivotal to opinion formation and information dissemination during the pandemic. This analysis is enriched with data from Facebook, Instagram, and traditional media to provide a comprehensive, cross-platform view of the phenomenon within the Brazilian context. The objective is to trace how various voices and interests shaped perceptions of Ivermectin during the pandemic’s early months.

Twitter data provides unique insight into real-time discussions, capturing the fluidity and heterogeneity of public opinion. By comparing narratives, keywords, and actors between the two periods, the analysis reveals a significant rise in politicized discourse surrounding Ivermectin and the predominance of mis/disinformation in discussions. The findings show how narratives shifted in response to emerging research, public statements, and government regulations.

The research demonstrates how social and political contexts influenced the perception and use of Ivermectin, offering critical insights into the intersections of public health, politics, and communication. This approach underscores the evolving dynamics of discourse during the pandemic, highlighting the role of mis/disinformation and political rhetoric in shaping public attitudes toward controversial medical treatments.

The struggle about masks and mask recommendation – Contestation of Finnish mask discussion on Twitter during the Covid-19 pandemic in 2020 and 2021 (online)

Kleber Carrilho, Emilia Palonen, Juha Koljonen, University of Helsinki

The mask discussions in Finland during 2020 and 2021 can be divided into three periods: pre-mask recommendation (spring 2020 - August 2020), normalized management (autumn 2020 - end of 2020), and consensus falling apart (end of 2020 - end of 2021). We focus on two main themes: Mask recommendation which emerged during the first period, and mask surveillance and anti-mask discussions which emerged during the second period.

Discussions about the need for a mask mandate began in March 2020, with themes including scientific arguments, international comparisons, and economic benefits. Opposition politicians and scientists criticized the government's lack of mask recommendations. From autumn 2020 onwards, discussions also focused on mask prices and the need for stricter mask recommendations for schools and children.

Anti-mask discussions in Finland centered on claims that masks are ineffective or dangerous, the pandemic is a hoax, mask mandates infringe on personal liberties, and government corruption. These discussions were minimal and only became noticeable in late December 2020. Mask surveillance discussions generally viewed mask-wearing as positive, emphasizing safety and responsibility. Criticism was directed at individuals not wearing masks and at entities not enforcing mask policies. Both anti-mask and mask surveillance discourses included accusations against politicians for not wearing masks.

Unequal Burdens: The Impact of Covid-19 on Brazil's Diverse Populations and Community Resilience

Aline Hasegawa, UNICAMP; **Thiago Brandão**, IESP-UERJ; **Cintia Nascimento**, UNICAMP; **Gabriela Villen**, UNICAMP

Despite the national expertise in controlling and fighting epidemics situations that could position Brazil as a global reference in addressing the Covid-19 pandemic, the country became the epicenter of deaths worldwide. This article has two distinct yet complementary objectives. The first aims to demonstrate, using microdata from SIVEP-Gripe, that the Covid-19 pandemic significantly impacted the lives and health of all individuals; however, the chances of surviving SARS-CoV-2 were and continue to be unevenly distributed among white, black, and indigenous populations. Using the community outreach work carried out by the Fórum de Comunidades Tradicionais da Bocaina as a research locus, the second objective seeks to identify, through ethnographic accounts, how indigenous and traditional communities organized solidarity networks to face the challenges posed by the pandemic.

Inter-scientificity, religiosity and traditional knowledge in the fight against Covid-19 among indigenous peoples on the Amazonian borders (online)

José Maria Trajano Vieira , UFAM

Resulting from a participatory action ethnographic research conducted before, during, and after the Covid-19 pandemic, this study describes and analyzes how Indigenous peoples who move across the tri-border region between Brazil, Peru, and Colombia—including the Kokama, Tikuna, Mayoruna, Marubo, and Kanamary, among others—mobilized to address the multifaceted challenges posed by the pandemic. These challenges encompassed public health, social, political, economic, religious, ideological, and ontological dimensions.

In the first analytical dimension, we examine state actions and omissions regarding the implementation of public policies in this border region, particularly contemporary Indigenous policies. This analysis intersects with forms of community resistance and resilience, as well as with the agency of individuals and Indigenous organizations that reinforced and established kinship networks and intra-ethnic and interethnic alliances. These alliances were formed with various social actors and institutions, including governmental and non-governmental entities, religious and secular organizations, extending beyond national borders.

In the second analytical dimension, despite the varied resources employed, shaped by cultural differences and specific historical and interethnic contact experiences, we explore how, in the Upper Solimões region and Javari Valley of the Brazilian Amazon, Indigenous peoples conceptualized Covid-19 based on their cosmologies and individual and collective subjectivities. They developed prevention and treatment strategies that reflect an articulation between academic and non-academic knowledge, Christian religiosity, and shamanic practices.

Rather than adopting a single, universal model as recommended by the World Health Organization (WHO), Indigenous communities in this region developed diverse strategies—some complementary, others mutually exclusive—grounded in traditional knowledge to address the health and humanitarian crisis.

Finally, we seek to bridge these two analytical dimensions, aiming to assess the consequences of Covid-19 among our Indigenous interlocutors.

Post-COVID Transformations in Culture, Social Structure and Policy in Relation to Mass Emergencies in Several American and European Countries

Ann Nguyen, Eric Jones, University of Texas

We look at how much societies in the ENDURE project changed as a result of the Covid-19 pandemic in terms of their orientation to mass emergencies. To do so, we devoted attention for 10 countries to three broad areas, including 1) changes within the culture or daily life of people in terms of expectations, preparedness, and attitudes, 2) social structural changes that relate to the roles and behaviors of groups of people and institutions for mass emergencies, and 3) policies. We suggest a typology of transformation in how societies relate to mass emergencies that takes into consideration the level of preparedness and impact as well as the role of economic changes due to Covid-19. Relatively unique or not-ubiquitous transformations included health (non-scientific approaches, mandatory vaccines for some populations), polarization/unity (avenue for creating partisan laws, attempts to protect rule of law, protests largely in countries lacking unity), inflation (minimum wage efforts, energy and housing subsidies), and immigration (focus on skilled workers or not, attention to borders, integration, limits on asylum).

Preliminary Findings from Cross-National Surveys on Experiences of the Covid-19 Pandemic, Political Attitudes, and Resilience

Kristinn Arsaelsson and Peter Ramand, Universidade de Wisconsin

We will present early results from the Endure survey conducted in the USA, UK, Germany, Poland, and Croatia. The survey examines individual and collective experiences during the Covid-19 pandemic, including descriptive, attitudinal, and behavioral dimensions. Respondents detailed their pandemic experiences including whether or not they, or members their family, were sick, the frequency of this, deaths in the family caused by Covid, access to tests, vaccines and other similar items. Attitudinal questions explored beliefs about Covid-19, the efficacy of vaccines, and the prevalence of conspiratorial attitudes within public opinion. The survey also investigates political mobilization and resilience, examining how individuals engaged with collective action during the pandemic. Additionally, preliminary analysis addresses broader ideological patterns, including left/right sentiments, and attitudes towards populism and nationalism. These findings offer insights into how the pandemic may have intersected with existing political and social belief systems across different national contexts. The presentation will focus on cross-national comparisons, highlighting key similarities and differences across the five countries, and point towards potential paths for future research.

Global Crisis and Local Livelihoods: Understanding Biographical Adjustments

Mihai Varga, FU Berlin

The paper discusses the conceptualization of individual resilience used in ENDURE's Cluster 2, a cluster of fieldwork studies in nine countries. It approaches individual resilience as situated between livelihood (work in the broadest sense) and the context that ensures its social embeddedness; the relationship between livelihood/work and its social context has formed the heart of a debate between approaches centering on the "capital" types supporting work and those that emphasize how the social structures that enable the reproduction of workers contribute to capitalist exploitation. Both camps - the Sustainable Livelihoods (SL) framework and Social Reproduction Theory (SRT) - have produced extensive literatures, and the former - SL - has left an indelible mark on poverty reduction programs and international organizations over three decades, notwithstanding the criticism it has received from the latter, SRT. ENDURE seeks to transcend this divide by demonstrating that a broader and divergent approach to the social relations addressed by SRT allows for new and more realistic insights into the "social" in social sustainability and sustainable livelihoods. Specifically, the paper argues that intra-household relations between genders and generations should be understood not only as labor boundaries or as underpinning capitalist exploitation but also as arrangements that both motivate and obligate (even compel) individuals to participate in markets for labor and services. The paper illustrates its argument with ethnographic material and interviews with migrant workers in the Romanian-Ukrainian border region.

Spatial-Temporal Analysis of Resilience to COVID in Europe and the Americas

Jingjing Gao, Eric Jones, University of Texas

This study presents a spatial-temporal analysis of resilience to Covid-19 in Europe and the Americas, exploring a variety of social, economic, and political factors influencing countries' ability to withstand and recover from the pandemic. Resilience is assessed in two primary dimensions: preparedness and economic recovery. Preparedness is evaluated based on Covid-19 infection and death rates at the onset of the pandemic and throughout its progression, while economic resilience is measured by how well countries' economies rebounded post-pandemic. Key factors examined include per capita income, race/ethnicity, education levels, population density, region, class, occupation, economic sector, health status, vaccine distribution, political polarization, and political party affiliation. The study categorizes countries into four resilience quadrants: high preparedness with low or high economic resilience, and low preparedness with low or high economic resilience. Using a spatial-temporal panel regression model, such as the Spatial Durbin Model (SDM), would allow this study to robustly analyze the resilience of countries to Covid-19 by considering both spatial and temporal factors. The Spatial Durbin Model (SDM) is well-suited for analyzing spatial dependencies in cross-sectional and temporal data. This model can account for geographic spatial spillover effects (i.e., how the resilience of one country might influence or be influenced by neighboring countries) and temporal dynamics (the evolution of resilience over time). The model can be extended to incorporate various covariates (economic, social, and political factors) and temporal elements (changes over the course of the pandemic), offering a deeper understanding of how these factors influence Covid-19 outcomes and recovery. By employing a spatial-temporal analysis, this study offers spatial insights into how these factors interact across countries, providing a deeper understanding of the conditions that shaped both immediate responses and long-term recoveries from the Covid-19 crisis.

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